

Extraction of copper(II) and lead(II) ions using liquid chelating ion exchanger : 2,4-undecanedione

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Manuscript received 7 March 2005, revised 19 September 2006, accepted 25 September 2006

Abstract : A liquid chelating ion exchanger (LCE) containing β -diketo group has been synthesized using octanoic acid ($C_8H_{16}O_2$) as the starting material and characterized by BP, FT-IR and UV-visible spectroscopy. The synthesized LCE was used for the extraction of Cu and Pb metal ions. Based on these studies, the optimum conditions for extraction of Cu and Pb metal ions from different effluents have been proposed.

Keywords : Copper(II), lead(II), liquid chelating ion-exchanger.

The present paper describes the synthesis, characterization and analytical applications of the liquid chelating ion exchanger (LCE) : 2,4-undecanedione. The synthesized ion exchanger has been characterized by b.p., density, FT-IR and UV-visible spectroscopy and used for the extraction of Cu and Pb metal ions. The concentration of the extracted metal ions is determined by AAS. Different parameters such as different concentration of LCE, metal ions and stripping agents have also been studied. Based on these studies the optimum conditions for recovery of Cu and Pb metal ions from different industrial effluents have been proposed.

Results and discussion

Molecular weight of synthesized LCE is 174, b.p. is 115 °C and density was 0.8644 g/ml.

λ_{max} for the LCE in $CHCl_3$ is 291 nm. It is well known that in α -diketones¹, enolic form is generally more stable than keto form. The absorption is related to the presence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl system. The calculated value of λ_{max} is ≈ 252 nm according to Woodward-Hoffman rules. A shift in λ_{max} (≈ 272) is expected in the presence of intermolecular H-bonding. λ_{max} is obtained at 291 nm in the present study. This shift i.e. from 272 to 291 nm, can be explained due to the formation of enolate ion.

FT-IR spectra of 'E' (Ester) and LCE shows sharp bands at 2962 cm^{-1} and at 1461 cm^{-1} corresponding to C-H alkane stretching and bending of methyl group re-

spectively. In addition to this, FT-IR spectra of 'E' shows a band at 1735 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of ester group and FT-IR of LCE shows bands at 1737 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} attributed to the presence of ketone group and β -diketone group respectively².

The % extraction of Cu metal ion using different concentration of LCE such as 0.2, 0.02 and 0.002 M was carried out. The concentration of the metal ion taken was from 10 ppm to 3 ppm. The stripping agent (HCl) used was 0.01 N. It was found that higher concentration of LCE does not affect the metal ion extraction. 0.02 M of the LCE give maximum % extraction (70%). The different concentrations of the Cu ion tried was from 50 ppm to 3 ppm. It is seen that % extraction increases as the concentration decreases. The maximum extraction of (70%) was seen for 3 ppm of the Cu ion solution. The used concentration of LCE is 0.02 M and stripping agent is 0.01 N.

The optimized conditions for the 100% extraction of Cu^{2+} and Pb^{2+} are $[LCE] = 0.02$ M for both with extraction time of 3 min; $[HCl] = 1.0$ and 0.5 N respectively. Recovery is 100% in both the cases.

The present LCE gives 97 and 98% recovery of Cu^{2+} and Pb^{2+} respectively from all effluents collected around Baroda.

Experimental

AnalaR quality chemicals were used throughout the experiment.

Synthesis of liquid chelating ion exchanger was carried out in two steps. The first step was the synthesis of the ester and the second step consists in converting the obtained ester into the liquid chelating ion exchanger (LCE). Octanoic acid mixed with ethanol was refluxed with small amount of sulphuric acid at 60 °C for 24 h in a round bottom flask with a double walled condenser. The ester formed was then distilled out and designated as 'E'.

The formed ester was mixed with excess of acetone in a round bottom flask fitted with double wall condenser. Na-ethoxide was added in required amount and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. The formed liquid chelating ion exchanger was distilled out and designated as LCE.

Stock solution of LCE was prepared in chloroform. 10 ml of 0.02 M LCE was mixed with 2 ml of the buffer solution (to adjust pH = 8) and 1 ml of 25 ppm metal ion solution containing Cu or Pb. The organic layer was sepa-

rated, washed 2 times with chloroform (10 ml) and then stripped with 1 N HCl solution to extract the metal ion. The mixture was shaken for 3 min and allowed to stand for 3 min. AAS was used for the determination of the metal ions.

Interference of metal ions : In the present study we have used of masking agents, thiourea-TETA 2% and thioglycolic acid 2% for Cu and Pb respectively for their analysis in presence of each other. The respective masking agent was added during pre-concentration, prior to determination by atomic absorption spectroscopy. The extraction of the metal ion was carried out following the same procedure under the optimum conditions.

A number of LCE³ have been reported for the extraction of Cu and Pb, but the Liquid Ion Exchanger containing β-diketone group are very few. Table 1 represents comparison for the present work with other reported LCE in order to show superiority and novelty of the present LCE. The ester formed in step one was characterized by FT-IR spectra. Liquid Chelating Exchanger (LCE) was characterized by boiling point, density, UV-visible spectroscopy and FT-IR spectra. FT-IR spectra of 'E' and LCE were carried out on Perkin-Elmer RX-1 using Nujol mull as a reference. UV-visible spectra was recorded on Shimadzu PR-1. The determinations of the metal ions from the standard solutions was carried out on AAS GBC-902. The parameters for the Cu ions on the AAS were set in the following two range; (i) 7.5–30 ppm, sensitivity was 0.16 and slit width is 0.2, (ii) 2.5–10 ppm, sensitivity was 0.05 and slit width was 0.5, λ = 217.9 nm, current was set at 3 amperes for both the ranges.

Conclusion : UV-visible and FT-IR confirms the presence of the diketone group in the synthesized LCE. The

Table 1. Comparison with other LCE's with β-diketone group

Sl. no.	Other LCE's	Concn. of metal ions	Conditions	Solvent used	Recovery (%)
1.	Versatic 10 (Pb)	6.6–9.0 ppm	0.1 M LCE	1,2-Dichloromethane	90
			0.1 N HNO ₃	Cyclohexanone	56.7
				Methyl isobutyl ketone	46
2.	Heptanoic acid (Pb) (in present study)	3 ppm	0.02 M LCE 0.5 N HCl	Chloroform	97–98 (Pb)
3.	Versatic 10 ²¹ (Cu)	0.5–9.0 ppm	1.6 × 10 ⁻³ mM LCE 0.03–3 N HCl	Chloroform	97.5– 102.5
4.	Heptanoic acid (Cu) (in present study)	3 ppm	0.02 M LCE 1 N HCl	Chloroform	96–97 (Cu)

data shows that very little amount of LCE, 10 ml, 0.02 M is required for 100% extraction of Cu^{2+} and Pb^{2+} . In addition very small concentration of both the metal ions, upto 3 ppm, can be determined by using present LCE.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Mr. Sumit, Geology Department, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, for doing AAS. One of the authors, (Ms.) Niki Vithlani, is also thankful to M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda for financial support.

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